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INNOVATSION
TERAPIYA**

**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

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**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

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*Учредитель Бухарский государственный
медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино*

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Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100,
г. Бухара, ул. А. Гиждувани, 23.

Телефон:

(99865) 223-00-50

Факс

(99866) 223-00-50

Сайт

<https://ivit.uz/>

e-mail

shnaimova5@gmail.com

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GENETIC STRUCTURE OF ACUTE MYELOID LEUKEMIA

EGAMOVA SITORA KOBILOVNA

Bukhara State Medical Institute. Bukhara. Uzbekistan.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8139-3376>

egamova.sitora@bsmi.uz

Annotation. Acute myeloid leukemia (AML) - is the most common acute leukemia among adults. The pathophysiology of the disease is associated with cytogenetic abnormalities, gene mutations and aberrant gene expression. Molecular genetic features of AML underlie the stratification of patients into risk groups and determination of treatment tactics. Chromosomal aberrations such as t(6;9)(p23;q34.1), DEK:NUP214, translocations involving the KMT2A gene (MLL), mutations in the RUNX1, TP53, ASXL1 genes are factors of unfavorable prognosis.

Keywords: acute myeloid leukemia, cytogenetics, mutation, translocation.

ГЕНЕТИЧЕСКОЕ СТРОЕНИЕ ОСТРЫХ МИЕЛОИДНЫХ ЛЕЙКОЗОВ

ЭГАМОВА СИТОРА КОБИЛОВНА

Бухарский государственный медицинский институт. Бухара. Узбекистан

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8139-3376>

egamova.sitora@bsmi.uz

Аннотация. Острый миелоидный лейкоз (ОМЛ) – наиболее распространенный острый лейкоз среди взрослых. Патопфизиология заболевания связана с цитогенетическими аномалиями, генными мутациями и aberrантной экспрессией генов. Молекулярно-генетические особенности ОМЛ лежат в основе стратификации больных на группы риска и определения тактики лечения. Такие хромосомные aberrации, как t(6;9)(p23;q34.1), DEK:NUP214, транслокации с участием гена KMT2A (MLL), мутации в генах RUNX1, TP53, ASXL1 являются факторами неблагоприятного прогноза.

Ключевые слова: острый миелоидный лейкоз, цитогенетика, мутация, транслокация.

ЎТКИР МИЕЛОИДЛИ ЛЕЙКОЗЛАРНИНГ ГЕНЕТИК ТУЗИЛИШИ ЭГАМОВА СИТОРА ҚОБИЛОВНА

Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти. Бухоро. Ўзбекистон

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8139-3376>

egamova.sitora@bsmi.uz

Аннотация. Ўткир миелоидли лейкоз (ЎМЛ) катталар орасида энг кенг тарқалган ўткир лейкоз ҳисобланади. Касалликнинг патофизиологияси цитогенетик аномалиялар, ген мутациялари ва аберрант ген экспрессияси билан боғлиқ. ЎМЛнинг молекуляр генетик хусусиятлари беморларни хавф гуруҳларига бўлиш ва даволаш тактикасини аниқлашга имкон беради. *DEK:NUP214*, *KMT2A (MLL)* гени иштирокидаги транслокациялар *t(6;9)(p23;q34.1)*, *RUNX1*, *TP53*, *ASXL1* генлари мутациялари каби хромосома абберацияси салбий прогноз омиллари ҳисобланади.

AML is a phenotypically and genetically heterogeneous disease. The current classification of the World Health Organization (2022) divides AML into separate nosological groups depending on cytogenetic and molecular genetic abnormalities [2]. Molecular genetic features of AML form the basis for stratifying patients into risk groups and determining treatment tactics [3]. Chromosomal aberrations such as *t(6;9)(p23;q34.1)*, *DEK:NUP214*, monosomic karyotype, *5/del(5q),7/del(7q),17/abn(17p)*, *inv(3)(q21.3q26.2)/t(3;3)(q21.3;q26.2)*, translocations involving the *KMT2A (MLL)* gene, except for *t(9;11)(p21.3;q23.3)*, *t(9;22)(q34.1;q11.2)/BCR:ABL1*, complex karyotype, mutations in the *RUNX1*, *TP53*, *ASXL1* genes are factors of unfavorable prognosis. On the contrary, the presence of such chromosomal abnormalities as *t(8;21)(q22;q22)/RUNX1:RUNX1T1* and *inv(16)(p13.1q22)/t(16;16)(p13.1;q22)/CBFB:MYH11* determines a favorable prognosis [3,6]. If intermediate-risk abnormalities or a normal karyotype are detected during cytogenetic testing, the prognosis group is determined by mutations in the *FLT3*, *NPM1*, *CEBPA*, *RUNX1*, *ASXL1*, and *TP53* genes (table 1). The presence of an *NPM1* mutation or a biallelic *CEBPA* mutation allows the patient to be assigned to the favorable risk group, however, *FLT3-ITD* (internal tandem duplication) mutations worsen the patient's prognosis, since they are associated with a high risk of relapse [7,9].

When stratifying patients into risk groups, not only the presence of the FLT3-ITD mutation is important, but also the allelic ratio of the mutant type to the “wild” type, which reflects the number of cells with a mutation or a mutant allele [10,12]. With an allelic load of $>0,5$ (FLT3-ITD_{high}) and the absence of the NPM1 mutation, the prognosis is defined as unfavorable [13,14]. The main principles of the classification were transferred to the new ELN classification of AML risk groups (2022), in which the spectrum of mutations with an unfavorable prognosis has expanded significantly [15]. Despite this, many mutational changes and their combinations, the stages of their occurrence, as well as a large number of other clinical- laboratory prognostic factors in AML cannot be accommodated by any of the modern classifications. At present, it is obvious that various types of mutations arise in hematopoietic stem cells, which complement each other and interact in leukemogenesis [16,17].

In recent years, mutations have been divided into several large functional types:

- type I mutations, which ensure the proliferation and viability of tumor cells. These are mutations of genes of signaling pathways (FLT3, c-KIT, NRAS/KRAS, NOTCH1/2, PTPN1, CBL, etc.);
- type II mutations affecting cell differentiation and apoptosis (CEBPA, GATA1/2, RUNX1, NPM1, TP53, as well as genes that arose by fusion: MLL(KMT2A)-r, CBFβ::MYH11, RUNX1::RUNX1T1, PML::RARA, etc.);
- type III mutations – mutations in genes of epigenetic regulation/modification (IDH1, IDH2, DNMT3A, TET2, HDACs, WT1, UTX, EZH2, ASXL1, BCOR, MLL-PTD, etc.).

Mutations in genes encoding RNA splicing proteins (SRSF2, SF3B1, U2AF1, ZRSR2, U2AF2, etc.) and cohesin proteins, a complex involved in the division of sister chromatids (STAG2, RAD21, SMC3, etc.), cell adhesion proteins (cadherins, integrins), ICAMs, CXCR4, etc., are classified into separate groups [18,20]. Many years of research have led us to understand that the process of mutation acquisition by a hematopoietic stem cell is sequential. Scientists have managed to identify the preleukemic stage of AML development, the so-called preleukemia. Primary (preleukemic) mutations are usually mutations of epigenetic regulators (type III), which shift the proliferative activity of hematopoietic stem cells towards self-renewal, which leads to the accumulation of a pathological clone in the bone marrow and peripheral blood; subsequent mutations of types I and II, driver mutations, directly cause the development of acute leukemia [24,26]. The most common preleukemic mutations in AML include mutations of the genes DNMT3A (15–25%), TET2 (8–12%), IDH1 (8–19%), IDH2 (7–14%) [6,15,16]. Mutations of DNMT3 A and TET2 play a leading role in the structure of clonal hematopoiesis in the elderly

[27]. The most common driver mutations in AML are inversions and translocations with the formation of chimeric transcripts CBFβ::MYH11 (5–8%), RUNX1::RUNX1T1 (4–5%), mutations with tandem duplication of the FLT3 gene (FLT3-ITD) (20–5%) or amino acid substitution in the kinase domain of the FLT3 receptor (FLT3-TKD) (5–7%), mutations of the NPM1 (27–35%) and CEBPA (5–6%) genes [15,16]. A frequent association of IDH1/2, DNMT3A, FLT3, NPM1 mutations is known [6]. One of the manifestations of tumor cell proliferation in AML is leukocytosis - the appearance of a large number of leukocytes in the peripheral blood, primarily due to immature, blast cells. Different authors define hyperleukocytosis as an absolute number of leukocytes $>100 \times 10^9/l$ in AML and $>50 \times 10^9/l$ in acute promyelocytic leukemia. Hyperleukocytosis worsens the patient's prognosis, since it triggers a number of pathogenetic mechanisms and can lead to DIC syndrome, leukostasis and tumor lysis syndrome [28]. With leukocytosis $>30 \times 10^9/l$, patients are shown prophylaxis of neuroleukemia [1]. To date, the association of some genetic events with the development of hyperleukocytosis and leukocytosis in AML has been proven. It has been shown that among patients with hyperleukocytosis/leukocytosis, patients with the myelomonocytic subtype of leukemia, NPM1 and FLT3-ITD mutations, chromosome 16 inversion, and chromosomal abnormality 11q23 are more common [8]. On the other hand, a number of studies have shown a negative impact of hyperleukocytosis and leukocytosis on long-term survival rates in AML both in the overall cohort of patients and in the favorable/intermediate risk group [8]. Since the pathogenesis of leukocytosis in AML remains the subject of close scientific attention, we investigated the genetic profile of AML occurring with leukocytosis.

Purpose of the study– assessment of the association of leukocytosis with the most common cytogenetic and genetic abnormalities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. The study included the material of 80 patients with AML, observed in the hematology department of the Bukhara Multidisciplinary Medical Center (Bukhara) from 2023 to 2024. The age of patients was 18-75 years, the median was 44 years. Inclusion criteria: confirmed AML, except for acute promyelocytic leukemia, the presence of cytogenetic study data, molecular genetic study of the FLT3, NPM1, CEBPA, IDH1/2, DNMT3A and TET2 genes or detected chimeric transcripts CBFβ::MYH11 and RUNX1::RUNX1T1 or the availability of archival DNA and RNA samples that allow studying these mutations. Favorable, intermediate, and unfavorable risk groups were determined according to the ELN classification (2017) [3]. Leukocytosis was defined as a leukocyte content in the

peripheral blood of $>30 \times 10^9/l$ at the time of disease manifestation. Clinical-laboratory characteristics of patients are presented (in table 2).

Study of IDH1/2, DNMT3A, FLT3-TKD gene mutations by allele-specific polymerase chain reaction. Point mutations of DNMT3A (p.R882H/C/S/P/L), IDH1 (p.R132H, p.R132C/G/S), IDH2 (p.R140Q, p.R172K), FLT3-TKD (p.D835Y) genes were determined by allele-specific polymerase chain reaction in real time on a Step One Plus RealTime PCR device (Applied Biosystems, USA).

Table 1. Molecular genetic stratification of patients with acute myeloid leukemia by ELN risk groups (2017)

Favorable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $t(8;21)(q22;q22), RUNX1::RUNX1T1$ • $inv(16)(p13.1q22), t(16;16)(p13.1;q22), CBF\beta::MYH11$ • Mutation <i>NPM1</i> without <i>FLT3-ITD</i> or with <i>FLT3-ITD</i>_{low} • Biallelic mutation <i>CEBPA</i>
Intermediate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mutation <i>NPM1</i> and <i>FLT3-ITD</i>_{high} • "Wild" type <i>NPM1</i> without <i>FLT3-ITD</i> or with <i>FLT3-ITD</i>_{low} (without genetic disorders classified as unfavorable) • $t(9;11)(p21.3;q23.3), MLLT3::KMT2A$ • Cytogenetic abnormalities not classified as favorable or unfavorable
Unfavorable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $t(6;9)(p23;q34.1), DEK::NUP214$ • $t(v;11q23.3),$ rearrangement <i>KMT2A</i> • $t(9;22)(q34.1;q11.2), BCR::ABL1$ • $inv(3)(q21.3q26.2), t(3;3)(q21.3;q26.2), GATA2::MECOM(EV11)$ • 5/del(5q), 7/del(7q), 17/abn(17p) • Complex karyotype, monosomic karyotype • "Wild" type <i>NPM1</i> and <i>FLT3ITD</i> high • Mutation <i>RUNX1, ASXL1, TP53</i>

Table 2. Distribution of patients by the number of leukocytes depending on the risk group and identified genetic and cytogenetic abnormalities (n = 214), n (%).

Indicator	leukocytes <30 × 109/l (n = 42 (28%))	leukocytes >30 × 109/l (n = 58 (72%))
Risk according to ELN 2017 classification:		
favorable	24 (52)	27 (48)
intermediate	12 (61)	17 (39)
adverse	4 (68)	14 (32)
Cytogenetic aberrations and molecular data		
Favorable risk group: t(8;21)(q22;q22), RUNX1:RUNX1T1 inv(16)(p13.1q22), CBFB:MYH11 mutation in the NPM1 gene without FLT3-ITD or with FLT3-ITD low biallelic mutation of CEBPA	5 (9) 6 (24) 15 (52) 3 (7)	9 (16) 1 (6) 21 (12) 1 (1)
Intermediate risk group: (9;11)(p21.3;q23.3); MLLT3:KMT2A mutations in the genes NPM1 and FLT3-ITD high <i>NPM1 or FLT3-ITD high mutations</i> "wild type" NPM1 without FLT3-ITD mutation or with FLT3-ITD low mutation unclassified cytogenetic and/or molecular anomalies	1 (2) 2 (2) 0 4 (7)	2 (6) 9 (8) 8 (10) 2 (2)
Unfavorable risk group: complex or monosomic karyotype 5/del(5q), 7/del(7q), 17/abn(17p) NPM1 "wild type" and mutation in the FLT3-ITD high gene t(v;11q23.3), KMT2A rearrangement other, including combined anomalies	1 (2) 1 (2) 0 4 (6) 0	0 1 (6) 1 (10) 2 (3) 1 (6)

Cytogenetic study. Standard cytogenetic examination of G-differentially stained chromosomes of bone marrow aspirate cells was performed after short-term culturing according to the standard protocol. When possible, 20 metaphases were analyzed. Chromosomes were classified according to the International Cytogenetic Nomenclature criteria. Fluorescence in situ hybridization was performed using commercial DNA probes to detect t(8;21)(q22;q22)/RUNX1:RUNX1T1, inv(16)(p13.1q22)/CBFB:MYH11, inv(3)(q21;q26.2)/ GATA2:MECOM, t(11q23;v)/KMT2A, 7/del(7q), 5/del(5q) depending on the results of standard cytogenetic and morphological research.

RESULTS. Leukocytosis $>30 \times 10^9/l$ was detected in 58 (42%) of 80 patients. The incidence of leukocytosis in risk groups according to the ELN classification (2017) was not statistically significant ($p > 0,05$). In the favorable, intermediate, and unfavorable risk groups, the proportion of patients with a leukocyte count of $>30 \times 10^9/l$ was 48, 39, and 32%, respectively. A decrease in the proportion of leukocytosis in the unfavorable risk group was observed due to patients with 5/del(5q), 7/del(7q), 17/abn(17p), complex, and monosomic karyotypes, who had a leukocyte count of $<30 \times 10^9/l$ in 96,5% (28 of 29) of cases. A statistical difference was shown in the number of patients with and without leukocytosis in the groups with the corresponding cytogenetic status ($p < 0,001$). The number of leukocytes in patients ($n = 9$) with KMT2A (MLL) rearrangements varied significantly from 1,7 to $97 \times 10^9/l$ (median $19,3 \times 10^9/l$). The group of patients with inv(16), in contrast to the t(8;21) translocation, was associated with a high number of leukocytes

When assessing the association of individual mutations with leukocytosis $>30 \times 10^9/l$, a significant association of leukocytosis with FLT3 mutation (4,58; $p = 0,0001$) was found, but not with mutations in the NPM1 genes (1,74; $p = 0,0784$). Leukocytosis was significantly more common among patients with a confirmed FLT3 mutation than among patients without it (63,5% versus 29,5%; $p < 0,0001$). It can also be noted that in the presence of NPM1 mutation, the proportion of patients with leukocytosis was 45%, in its absence - 35% ($p = 0,0825$), and in the case of CEBPA mutation - 46 and 40% in its presence and absence, respectively ($p = 0,7518$). Mutations of the genes of epigenetic factors IDH1/2, DNMT3A were not associated with high levels of leukocytes (OR 0,99; $p = 0,9818$ and OR 1,62; $p = 0,2326$, respectively). Leukocytosis occurred in 39% of patients in the presence of a mutation and in 37% in its absence ($p = 1,0000$). In the presence of a DNMT3A mutation, leukocytosis was detected more often than in its absence, but the differences between the groups were not statistically significant (53% versus 33%; $p = 0,2947$).

Chromosome 16 inversion with formation of chimeric CBFB:MYH11 transcript

was statistically significantly associated with leukocytosis (OR 15,83; $p = 0,0001$), whereas $t(8;21)(q22;q22)$ translocation with formation of RUNX1::RUNX1T1 transcript demonstrated an association with leukocyte count $<30 \times 10^9/l$ (OR 0,06; $p = 0,0001$). Among patients with chimeric CBFβ:MYH11 transcript, leukocytosis was observed in 80% of cases, without it – in 23% ($p < 0,0001$); among patients with chimeric RUNX1:RUNX1T1 transcript, on the contrary, – 23 and 80%, respectively ($p < 0,0001$). Based on the results of multivariate logistic regression with stepwise selection, the following factors were selected as the most significant: FLT3 mutation and CBFβ:MYH11 chimeric transcript.

According to the results of univariate frequency analysis, the NPM1 mutation was weakly associated with leukocytosis ($p = 0,0784$) and was not selected for the model, since it did not reach the required threshold level of significance. Thus, our results are consistent with the data of other researchers [14,16] on the frequent association of FLT3 and CBFβ::MYH11 with leukocytosis. However, we did not find a connection between mutations in the CEBPA, IDH1/2, DNMT3A genes separately and the development of leukocytosis.

We analyzed the relationship between the white blood cell count and the FLT3-ITD allelic ratio in 44 patients. No statistically significant correlation was found (Spearman correlation coefficient 0,45; $p = 0,0019$).

Patients ($n=29$) with intermediate-risk karyotype, normal karyotype and unclassified cytogenetic abnormalities were separately identified from this cohort. In this group, similar values were obtained: the lowest leukocyte levels were observed in patients with IDH1/2, DNMT3A, TET2 mutations (median $3,70 \times 10^9/l$; 95% CI $0,96-10,64 \times 10^9/l$), patients without identified mutations had slightly higher leukocyte levels (median $6,30 \times 10^9/l$; 95% CI $10,59-40,83 \times 10^9/l$), however, in groups 3 and 4, the number of leukocytes was significantly higher (median $23,78 \times 10^9/l$; 95% CI $28,92-59,70 \times 10^9/l$ and median $47,00 \times 10^9/l$; 95% CI $47,31-93,52 \times 10^9/l$ respectively).

A group of patients without identified mutations of IDH1/2, DNMT3A, TET2, FLT3, NPM1, CEBPA, in which a significant variation in leukocyte levels was observed, requires separate discussion. This group includes patients with rarer genetic and cytogenetic disorders, which are subject to further study in order to obtain adequate statistical data. In all cases, the differences in the number of leukocytes between groups with different genetic profiles, calculated using the Kruskal-Wallis test, were statistically significant ($p < 0,0001$).

CONCLUSION. Mutations FLT3 ($p < 0,0001$) and $inv(16)$ genes, CBFβ: MYH11 ($p = 0,0009$) were most associated with the development of leukocytosis $> 30 \times 10^9/l$ in

AML, while (8; 1) / RUNX1:: RUNX1T1 and unfavorable cytogenetic abnormalities such as 5 / del (5q), 7/del (7q), 17/abn (17p), complex and monosomic karyotype were significantly associated with low leukocyte levels at the time of disease manifestation ($p < 0,0001$). In the intermediate cytogenetic risk group, leukocytosis was associated with a combination of mutations in the genes of epigenetic factors IDH1/ 2, DNMT3A, TET2 and mutations in FLT3, NPM1, CEBPA ($p < 0,0001$). This result can be explained by the combined effect of mutations on the proliferative potential of tumor cells.

LITERATURE

1. Pekhova K.A., Sidorova Yu.V. Genetic landscape of acute myeloid leukemia occurring with leukocyte // Oncohematology.- 2023. № 3.- P.102-114. (In Russ.).

2. Khoury JD, Solary E., Abla O. et al. The 5th edition of the World Health Organization classification of haematolymphoid tumors: myeloid and histiocytic/dendritic neoplasms. *Leukemia* 2022;36(7):1703–19. DOI: 10.1038/s41375022016131

3. Döhner H., Estey E., Grimwade D. et al. Diagnosis and management of AML in adults: 2017 ELN recommendations from an international expert panel. *Blood* 2017;129(4):424–47.

4. Grimwade D., Hills RK, Moorman AV et al. Refinement of cytogenetic classification in acute myeloid leukemia: determination of prognostic significance of rare recurring chromosomal among 5876 younger adult patients treated in the United Kingdom Medical Research Council trials. *Blood* 2010;116(3):354–65. DOI: 10.1182/blood200911254441

5. Grimwade D., Walker H., Harrison G. et al. The predictive value of hierarchical cytogenetic classification in older adults with acute myeloid leukemia (AML): analysis of 1065 patients entered into the United Kingdom Medical Research Council AML11 trial. *Blood* 2001;98(5):1312–20. DOI: 10.1182/blood.v98.5.1312

6. Nemirovchenko VS, Shervashidze MA, Valiev TT, Kondratchik KL Treatment results of pediatric acute myeloid leukemia with epigenetic drugs addition. *Onkogematologiya = Oncohematology* 2020;15(2):19–28. (In Russ.).

7. Kottaridis PD, Gale RE, Frew ME et al. The presence of a FLT3 internal tandem duplication in patients with acute myeloid leukemia (AML) adds important prognostic information to cytogenetic risk group and response to the first cycle of chemotherapy: analysis of 854 patients from the United

Kingdom Medical Research Council AML 10 and 12 trials. *Blood* 2001;98(6):1752–9. DOI: 10.1182/blood.v98.6.1752.

8.Thiede C., Steudel C., Mohr B. et al. Analysis of FLT3 activating mutations in 979 patients with acute myelogenous leukemia: association with FAB subtypes and identification of subgroups with poor prognosis. *Blood* 2002;99(12):4326–35. DOI: 10.1182/blood.v99.12.4326

9.Fröhling S., Schlenk RF, Breitruck J. et al. Prognostic significance of activating FLT3 mutations in younger adults (16 to 60 years) with acute myeloid leukemia and normal cytogenetics: a study of the AML Study Group Ulm. *Blood* 2002;100(13):4372–80. DOI: 10.1182/blood2002051440

10.Pratcorona M., Brunet S., Nomdedéu J. et al. Favorable outcome of patients with acute myeloid leukemia harboring a lowallelic burden FLT3-ITD mutation and concomitant NPM1 mutation:relevance to postremission therapy. *Blood* 2013;121(14):2734–8. DOI: 10.1182/blood201206431122

11.Schlenk RF, Kayser S, Bullinger L et al. Differential impact of allelic ratio and insertion site in FLT3-ITD positive AML with respect to allogeneic transplantation. *Blood* 2014;124(23):3441–9. DOI: 10.1182/blood201405578070

12.Lynch DC, Hills RK, Burnett AK et al. Impact of FLT3-(ITD) mutant allele level on relapse risk in intermediate risk acute myeloid leukemia. *Blood* 2014;124(2):273–6. DOI: 10.1182/blood201402554667

13.Gale RE, Green C, Allen C et al. The impact of FLT3 internal tandem duplication mutant level, number, size, and interaction with NPM1 mutations in a large cohort of young adult patients with acute myeloid leukemia. *Blood* 2008;111(5):2776–84. DOI: 10.1182/blood200708109090

14.Döhner K., Thiede C., Jahn N. et al. Impact of NPM1/FLT3ITD genotypes defined by the 2017 European LeukemiaNet in patients with acute myeloid leukemia. *Blood* 2020;135(5):371–80. DOI: 10.1182/blood.2019002697

15.Döhner H., Wei AH, Appelbaum FR et al. Diagnosis and management of AML in adults: 2022 recommendations from an international expert panel on behalf of the ELN. *Blood* 2022;140(12):1345–77. DOI: 10.1182/blood.2022016867

16.Cancer Genome Atlas Research Network. Genomic and epigenomic landscapes of adult de novo acute myeloid leukemia. *N Engl J Med* 2013;368(22):2059–74. DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa1301689

17.Bullinger L., Döhner K., Döhner H. Genomics of acute myeloid leukemia diagnosis and pathways. *J Clin Oncol* 2017;35(9):934–46. DOI: 10.1200/JCO.2016.71.2208

18.Kelly LM, Gilliland DG Genetics of myeloid leukemias. *Annu Rev Genomics Hum Genet* 2002;3:179–98. DOI: 10.1146/annurev.genom.3.032802.115046

19.Panuzzo C., Signorino E., Calabrese C. et al. Landscape of tumor

- suppressor mutations in acute myeloid leukemia. *J Clin Med* 2020;9(3):802. DOI: 10.3390/jcm9030802
- 20.**LagunasRangel FA, ChávezValencia V., GómezGuijosa M.Á., CortesPenagos C. Acute myeloid leukemiagenetic alterations and their clinical prognosis. *Int J Hematol Oncol Stem Cell Res* 2017;11(4):328–39.
- 21.**Block M., Jacobson LO, Bethard WF Preleukemic acute human leukemia. *J Am Med Assoc* 1953;152:1018–28. DOI: 10.1001/jama.1953.03690110032010
- 22.**Medinger M., Passweg JR Acute myeloid leukaemia genomics. *Br J Haematol* 2017;179(4):530–42. DOI: 10.1111/bjh.14823
- 23.**Koeffler HP, Leong G. Preleukemia: one name, many meanings. *Leukemia* 2017;31(3):534–42. DOI: 10.1038/leu.2016.364
- 24.**Bowman RL, Busque L., Levine RL Clonal hematopoiesis and evolution to hematopoietic malignancies. *Cell Stem Cell* 2018;22(2):157–70. DOI: 10.1016/j.stem.2018.01.011
- 25.**Vergez F., Largeaud L., Bertoli S. et al. Phenotypically defined stages of leukemia arrest predict main driver mutations subgroups, and outcome in acute myeloid leukemia. *Blood Cancer J* 2022;12(8):117. DOI: 10.1038/s41408022007127
- 26.**Kishtagari A., Levine RL, Viny AD Driver mutations in acute myeloid leukemia. *Curr Opin Hematol* 2020;27(2):49–57. DOI: 10.1097/MOH.0000000000000567
- 27.**Genovese G., Kähler AK, Handsaker RE et al. Clonal hematopoiesis and bloodcancer risk inferred from blood DNA sequence. *N Engl J Med* 2014;371(26):2477–87. DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa1409405
- 28.**Troitskaya VV, Parovichnikova EN, Sokolov AN et al. Treatment of adult patients with acute myeloid leukemia with hyperleukocytosis at the onset of the disease. *Terapevticheskiy arkhiv /Therapeutic Archive* 2015;87(7):33–40.
- 29.**Bewersdorf JP, Zeidan AM Hyperleukocytosis and leukostasis in acute myeloid leukemia: can a better understanding of the underlying molecular pathophysiology lead to novel treatments? *Cells* 2020;9(10):2310. DOI: 10.3390/cells9102310
- 30.**Stahl M., Shallis RM, Wei W. et al. Management of hyperleukocytosis and impact of leukapheresis among patients with acute myeloid leukemia (AML) on short and longterm clinical outcomes: a large, retrospective, multicenter, international study. *Leukemia* 2020;34(12):3149–60. DOI: 10.1038/s4137502007833